

DEVELOPMENT OF A TESTING METHOD FOR VIBRATION FATIGUE AT RESONANCE

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue testing of composite materials is a complex area of research. Although testing methods using hydraulic machines are well-established, they can be prohibitive in terms of time and also they do not take into account dynamic effects. In this manuscript a testing methodology for characterizing the fatigue behaviour of composite components under resonant conditions is described. The most relevant mechanical and dynamic parameters are captured using this method. Specifically, specimen's temperature profiles from experimental data are examined and correlated with other dynamic responses, such as natural frequency decay and Operating Deflection Shapes (ODS). Finally an S-N curve by the mean of displacement is shown.

1 INTRODUCTION

The fatigue behavior of Fiber-Reinforced Plastic (FRP) has been studying for more than thirty years, since they took part in projects as structural materials [1]. Talreja in 2008 [2] reviewed the developments in research of fatigue in composites since the 80s. The "fatigue life diagrams" were described as the starting point from which the first S-N curves by the mean of strains were built. Thereafter, in the 90s, that macro-scale point of view did not fit the requirements of a quantitative model for predicting failure, pushing the research towards micro-scale approach, such as the variational approach [3]–[5] and the shear lag theory [6], [7].

At the other side of the spectrum, the micro-scale analysis was too limiting, in terms of studied configurations and of damage evaluation. In fact, microcracking is a complex phenomenon that appears during the early stage of the fatigue life, which does not lead to a significant decrease in ultimate strength or stiffness. Instead, the fatigue characterization focussed on Paris law based theories [8] which allow more ready-to-use data of delamination growth rate, and which take into account phenomena that significantly degrade the component strength, such as delamination and debonding.

As it is often the case, the key bottleneck of the research is the experimental validation. Fatigue tests are usually carried out at frequency lower than 10 Hz [4], [9]–[11], (with few cases up to 25 Hz [12]) to avoid self-heating effect and to meet the operative range of the hydraulic machines. That experimental environment is as convenient as limiting, being standardized but time consuming. To increase the cost-efficiency, as it was done with metals [13], the test could be carried out at resonance [14], [15], exploiting the dynamics of the structure so as to amplify the loading condition at high frequencies. This manuscript deals with the testing methodology for characterizing the fatigue behaviour of composite components. It describes an improvement of the contact method showed in Ref. [14], analysing some preliminary results, and discussing the advantages that the testing methods implies.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

One major outcome in Ref. [14] is that by engineering a mode shape using opportune weights either side of the clamping, one can modify the loads distribution, reaching higher strains than a simpler configuration (see Figure 1). This test configuration integrated with a specific component feature lead to the development of a more robust one. The component used here is designed to vibrate at the first bending mode, clamped within two rods to minimize the contact area to a line, with a weight fixed in one side in respect with the rods (see Figure 2). It is a rectangular specimen, 100 mm wide and 260 mm long, with the weight at 50 mm from one edge along the length, clamped at 110 mm and with ply drops in the centreline, at 130 mm. The layup is $[0, 0_{\text{drop}}, 90_{\text{drop}}, (0, 90)_3, 0]_s$, designed following the considerations of Maccagnano et Al. [16]:

- The ply drop is a likely place from which a delamination could initiate
- Two or more ply drops intensify the stress concentration factor (especially in the outer faces when the specimen is subjected to bending)
- The first two plies in the thick section are oriented in the 0° direction to increase the actual strength under the clamp.
- To drop a ply at the outer face lead to an early delamination.

Figure 1 - (a) The specimen used for tests in Ref. [14] was designed to have a (b) asymmetric strain energy distribution over the length.

Figure 2 - Fixture set-up

A software, coded in LabVIEW, was used for the testing campaign. This software was specifically designed to carry out tests automatically. The flowchart in Figure 3 shows the process of the software from the modal test to the endurance test. According to it, the software performs the Frequency Response Functions (FRFs) at the beginning and at the end of the test for generating Bode plots, magnitude and phase, respectively. From this step it is possible to define a phase and a frequency at which the endurance test will run. As the termination criterion, the first occurrence between a natural frequency drop of 6% and a 10 million cycles run is considered.

Alongside the termination criteria, the software acts on the tests by using two controllers: the Phase Lock Loop (PLL) and an amplitude controller. Choosing the target phase and the target mode, the controller locks the phase between the input and the output by changing the excitation frequency. As soon as the output phase exceeds an upper and lower threshold spaced apart the target phase, the controller is activated. The amplitude control is based on the same principle. In addition, during the endurance test, ODSs are regularly measured by step-scanning the component. The aim of this is to capture any changes in ODSs by the delamination propagation.

Five specimens were tested, and five main recordings were considered in this study:

- Resonant frequency decay
- Temperature variation
- Changes in ODS during the endurance
- C-scan of the delaminated specimen
- Changes in vibration amplitude response before and after the endurance.

Figure 3 - Process flowchart

3 RESULTS

As mentioned, five main recording were considered for five specimens. In this section the outcomes will be presented and compared.

The most common way to monitor the damage evolution in fatigue tests is to measure the residual stiffness of the component. In a dynamic environment that means to monitor the resonant frequency decay for different loading severities. Besides, capturing the surface temperature of the component, one can correlate the drops in frequency with the temperature peaks (to compare Figure 4 and Figure 5). In fact, a sudden energy release occurs because of ply to ply frictioning resulting from delamination, this physical behavior leads to local increase of temperature of the component [17]. From Figure 5 and Figure 6 one can observe how the temperature could help to identify the damage onset temporally (maximum temperature evolution over number of cycles) and spatially (thermal images).

Test 2 was carried out at a low vibration amplitude, experiencing a low self-heating effect and without changing its natural frequency. It was the only test which was run for 10 million cycles without developing damage. By comparing the last thermal image of the sequences of Figure 6, with the C-scans shown in Figure 7, can be also noticed that the silhouettes of the hotspots and of the C-scans match well.

Figure 4 - Compared frequency decays

Figure 5 - Compared temperature profiles

Figure 6 - Thermal images for (Ref) Test 2, (a) Test 1, (b) Test 3, (c) Test 4 and (d) Test 5

Figure 7 - C-scan for (Ref) Test 2, (a) Test 1, (b) Test 3, (c) Test 4 and (d) Test 5

An important parameter to take into account in vibration fatigue is the strain field in the component. Thanks to the proposed method it was possible to observe that the strain distribution change with the delamination growth, making difficult the correlation between strain level and damage propagation.

During the tests, ODSs were acquired to capture any changes in the vibration. The time sequence for Test 5 is shown in Figure 8. After the delamination onset, it propagated mostly on the left side of the component (to compare with Figure 6(d) and Figure 8(d)), without altering the right edge. This occurrence made the first natural mode unbalanced, reason being the left side more compliant than the right one. The strain distribution varied accordingly, breaking any correlation between constant vibration amplitude and constant severity level.

The previous statement lead to the assumption that any S-N curve by the mean of strain, stress or displacement (Figure 9) can only be drawn prior to the first delamination onset.

Figure 8 - Time sequence of ODSs for Test 5. The square shows the first ODS to be deformed by a delamination

Figure 9 - S-N curve by the mean of displacement

Figure 10 – Vibration response to different excitation levels (Volts to the shaker) before the endurance (a) and after the endurance (b) for Test 1.

Figure 10 shows one more outcome of the testing campaign. The nonlinear behavior of the specimen is enhanced by the presence of a delamination, leading to a stiffer structure by increasing the vibration level, though the absolute stiffness is much lower than the pristine case.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A testing method for vibration fatigue at resonance is here proposed. It aims to perform fatigue testing by exploiting the dynamic behavior of the structure. From the outcomes one can see that the resonant frequency decay can be easily monitored by locking the phase angle between excitation and response. This parameter provides a way to capture changes in the component stiffness, connected to the structural degradation.

However, the structural degradation cannot be defined by one variable such as the resonance frequency. The experimental method presented in here shows that the additional recordings can help the understanding of the fatigue behavior and its complexity. The surface temperature is a good indicator of delamination onset and propagation, therefore it could allow contactless health monitoring. More information are given by the ODS measurement. The Laser Doppler Velocimeter (LDV) could record the vibration time sequences of some component point to capture nonlinearities and change in mode shape. Both of them could result in a different strain distribution which may change the service life of the component.

Alongside the ability of capturing all these parameters automatically, the strength of this procedure lays on the cost-efficiency. Furthermore, it can be applied directly to a component to emulate the actual loading condition.

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